

Integrating spatial risk analysis into sustainable territorial development: A complex approach in the context of the Shaki-Zagatala economic region

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Abstract

Strengthening the interrelations between spatial risk analysis and sustainable territorial development has emerged in recent years as one of the key directions in geographical and socio-economic research. This study employs a complex approach to ensure the integration of spatial risk factors into sustainable territorial development processes. The Shaki-Zagatala economic region of the Republic of Azerbaijan was selected as the pilot area within the framework of the research. In the contemporary context of increasing natural and technogenic risks, global climate change, and the growing complexity of socio-economic and territorial development processes, the importance of spatial risk analysis and management defines the relevance of this research. This study investigates the spatio-temporal dynamics of natural-technological processes occurring between 1950 and 2024 in the six administrative districts (Shaki, Zagatala, Gabala, Balaken, Oghuz, and Gakh) of the Shaki-Zagatala economic region. Statistical analyses are conducted to explore the relationship between population density and the intensity of natural-technological disasters. By applying a combination of advanced spatial-statistical methods, such as the Moran's I, Getis-Ord G_i^* and Analytic Hierarchy Process, the study aims to evaluate the correlation between population density and disaster frequency, identifying high-risk areas and their temporal patterns. In the presented article, as a result of the complex studies conducted to achieve the set objectives, a map of the spatial distribution of natural disaster risks in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region has been developed. The results obtained allow for the identification of the area's risk profile and the establishment of key priorities for long-term growth. A strategic planning model has been developed based on the identified opportunities and challenges in the field of sustainable territorial development.

Key words: Anthropogenic hazards, management, natural disaster risk assessment, Republic of Azerbaijan, socio-economic development, spatial risk mapping, statistical analysis, territorial planning

Academic editor: Mariyana Nikolova

Received: 22 May 2025

Accepted: 26 September 2025

Published: 30 October 2025

Citation: Alakbarova S (2025)

Integrating spatial risk analysis into sustainable territorial development: A complex approach in the context of the Shaki-Zagatala economic region.

Journal of the Bulgarian Geographical Society 53: 157–186. <https://doi.org/10.3897/jbgs.e159882>

[org/10.3897/jbgs.e159882](https://doi.org/10.3897/jbgs.e159882)

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1. Introduction

Spatial risk analysis has become a critical component in the planning and management of sustainable territorial development, especially in the context of increasing natural and anthropogenic hazards. As regions face growing chal-

allenges related to environmental vulnerability, socio-economic disparities, and climate-induced risks, the integration of spatial risk data into territorial development strategies is essential for fostering resilience, security, and balanced growth. This study aims to contribute to the formation of sustainable development models by conducting a complex spatial risk assessment tailored to the specific natural-geographic, socio-economic, and ecological characteristics of the Shaki-Zagatala economic region of Azerbaijan.

This study presents a complex approach to integrating spatial risk analysis into sustainable territorial development. The study adopts a complex methods approach, combining conceptual model building with empirical spatial analysis. The methodology is structured into four main phases.

In regions such as the Shaki-Zagatala economic zone, which are particularly vulnerable to environmental and geographical risks, such research provides a solid foundation for optimizing territorial governance and implementing proactive planning solutions. In the contemporary era, climate change, increasing natural and technogenic risks, as well as rapid urbanization and population growth, necessitate the application of new and complex approaches to spatial governance. Environmental and societal transformations during the medieval period in the region significantly enhanced communities' resilience and adaptive capacity in response to climatic fluctuations, while also contributing substantially to cultural and social development (Moran 1948; Ashraf and Ahmad 2021; Spampinato et al. 2022; Anwar et al. 2023; Kaimuldinova et al. 2025).

The main objective of the study is to analyze the interaction between potential risks and socio-economic factors, and to identify development prospects for the region. Furthermore, the study aims to assess the role of natural and technogenic disaster risks in shaping these prospects and to propose effective approaches to ensure sustainable development.

To support environmental protection goals, large-scale analyses must account for spatial and temporal confounding factors, and apply precautionary measures during data interpretation to minimize methodological uncertainties, thereby ensuring the reliability and consistency of the results (El-kenawy et al. 2022; Ashraf and Khalid 2022; Nikolova and Patarchanova 2024; Korohoda and Kupach 2024; Benedetti-Cecchi et al. 2010). Expanding the scope of climatic variables in observational studies and ensuring long-term data collection across diverse environments can substantially enhance the precision of hydrometeorological modeling under shifting atmospheric conditions, thereby informing region-specific strategies for sustainable resource management (Frag et al. 2016; Makhmudov 2017; Khalilov and Eminov 2024; Anwar et al. 2024; Aldughairi et al. 2025). Accurate analysis of spatial risks and their integration into sustainable territorial development is of critical importance, both in terms of regional planning and national security. In particular, spatially-informed decision-making is essential for minimizing the impacts of natural disasters and enhancing the resilience of both populations and territories. Therefore, aligning spatial risk analysis with sustainable development strategies is not only a scientific innovation but also a practical necessity.

To ensure a comprehensive and dynamic assessment of debris flow risks, future studies should consider integrating socio-spatial variables into their analytical frameworks. These variables may include livelihood types, particularly agricultural practices, as well as settlement patterns, especially in heterogeneous mountainous

regions where land use and economic activities vary considerably (Rustamov 1960; Babakhanov 2009; Tarikhazer et al. 2013, 2023; Alakbarova 2024a; He et al. 2025). Agricultural expansion, deforestation, and slope modification associated with rural livelihoods may intensify surface instability and water runoff, thereby exacerbating flow-related hazards (Gong et al. 2016; Aksoy et al. 2018; Timoshenko and Chernukha 2021; Pan et al. 2021; Alengebawy et al. 2021; Alakbarova 2024b).

Moreover, greater emphasis must be placed on high-risk circulation and accumulation zones, which are particularly vulnerable to debris flow impacts due to intensified human interventions, including urban development and land conversion. Enhancing the sustainability of agricultural regions under increasing climate risks and socio-economic uncertainty requires the integration of spatial risk analysis, early warning systems, and efficient land-use planning to support adaptive capacity and long-term territorial resilience (Tilman et al. 2002; Eyyubov 2008; Darnhofer et al. 2010; Mekhilef et al. 2013; Alakbarova 2024a; Petrevska and Andreeski 2024).

The comprehensive analysis of spatial risk factors and their influence on sustainable territorial development processes holds significant scientific and practical value in terms of reducing risks and enhancing resilience at the regional level. In this context, the conducted research is particularly relevant as it contributes to identifying the spatial structure of existing risks and provides a scientific basis for informed decision-making in risk management and territorial planning.

The present-day relief of the Shaki-Zagatala economic region of Azerbaijan is a complex morphodynamic system, subjected to significant anthropogenic load at the end of the second millennium. Changes in the dynamic state of relief can be both reversible and irreversible, hereditary and non-hereditary, occur under the influence of both natural and anthropogenic factors.

In the context of sustainable territorial development, the consideration of spatial risk factors is particularly critical in regions characterized by natural hazards such as seismic activity, landslides, and debris flows. The Shaki-Zagatala economic region of the Republic of Azerbaijan stands out with its distinct physical-geographical and socio-economic characteristics, making it a pertinent case for spatial risk assessment. Identifying the interactions between spatial risk patterns and sustainable development strategies in this region is essential for improving regional planning and enhancing resilience to natural hazards. Accordingly, this study aims to develop and substantiate a comprehensive methodological framework that integrates spatial risk analysis into sustainable territorial development strategies for the Shaki-Zagatala region.

The primary objective of this study is to develop a methodological framework based on spatial risk analysis and to ensure its effective integration into sustainable territorial development strategies. To achieve this aim, the research seeks to address the following core questions:

- How do spatial risk factors influence sustainable development processes within the Shaki-Zagatala economic region?
- What indicators can be used to evaluate the spatial distribution of natural and technogenic hazards across the region?
- How can priority intervention zones be identified based on the analysis of risk and vulnerability levels?
- In what ways can these assessments be integrated into regional sustainable planning and policy-making?

2. Methods

A variety of scientific approaches were employed within the framework of this study. In the initial phase, mathematical analysis and statistical evaluation methods were applied to systematize and generalize existing statistical data. Subsequently, correlation analysis based on engineering-geological and socio-economic indicators was conducted. This approach aims at scientifically substantiating the prevention, management, and defence measures against hazardous natural processes. As a result of the analyses, specific proposals were made, thematic graphs were prepared, and a map and an integrated assessment model reflecting risk zones were developed. Throughout these stages, Geographic Information System (GIS) technologies and satellite image decryption technologies were extensively used.

Data collection and preliminary spatial analysis – The first phase involved the collection of relevant spatial and statistical data. These include physical and geographical indicators (topography, soil types, hydrology), demographic distribution, economic activity zones, and existing infrastructure networks. Data were sourced from governmental open-access databases, satellite imagery, and regional planning documents. The collected data were processed using geographic information systems software such as ArcGIS, enabling initial spatial analyses. The risk and resilience characteristics of the study area were visually mapped.

This approach allowed for the identification and mapping of natural and technogenic hazards, facilitating the analysis of risk characteristics in the region. Through visual analysis of hazards and exposure indicators, high-risk areas were identified within the region. Within this framework, the Moran's I, Getis-Ord G_i^* and Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) were applied to assign weights to the risk criteria, ensuring a balanced consideration of both natural and anthropogenic factors. Additionally, spatial clustering and hot spot analysis techniques were applied to statistically identify areas with high concentrations of risk. This methodological approach provides a scientifically grounded basis for integrating risk analysis into territorial development strategies, thereby contributing to more resilient and sustainable spatial planning.

Moran's I has been identified as a more robust indicator. In this context, the study investigates the spatial dynamics of urban districts in relation to urban vehicle movement (Moran 1948; Chen 2013; Fisher 2013; Maruyama 2015; Wang et al. 2023; Yamada 2024; Isnan 2025).

Although Moran's I index is useful for distinguishing crash clusters, it has limitations in identifying specific hot and cold spots. Therefore, the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic is applied to more precisely detect areas of high and low spatial concentration, accounting for both event frequency and spatial correlation (Ord and Getis 1995, 2001; Songchitrukha and Zeng 2010; Rossi and Becker 2019; Lanorte et al. 2024; Rybalova et al. 2024).

In the AHP, the reliability of decision-making depends heavily on the precision with which pairwise comparison matrices are developed. The consistency ratio, employed within the hierarchical structure, functions as a threshold to assess the logical soundness of these matrices. If the consistency index surpasses the acceptable boundary, the corresponding evaluations must be reviewed (Saaty 1987; Saaty and Vargas 2001; Ishizaka and Labib 2009; Calabrese et al. 2019; Ansari et al. 2020; Darvishi et al. 2020; Duleba 2022; Tavana et al. 2023).

Within this study, spatial assessment and mapping of ecosystem services were conducted, focusing on the conservation and efficient use of ecosystems. The methodological approach aimed to support land-use planning processes by promoting the sustainable utilization of low-risk zones (Sokal and Thomson 1987; Savvinova et al. 2016; Borisova et al. 2023; Hajiyeva 2024).

3. Data sources and software

3.1. Spatial data analysis

To achieve the objectives of the study, data from various sources within the Shaki-Zagatala economic region was analyzed. The research database is based on the following sources:

- Spatial planning documents—the existing spatial planning documents of the Shaki-Zagatala region provided information about the key directions of infrastructure and socio-economic development in the area. The spatial planning documents concerning the Shaki-Zagatala region are an important source for this study. They provide essential information on the region's infrastructure and socio-economic development priorities.
- Statistics and data—data provided by the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Ministry of Emergency Situations has served as a fundamental source for demographic structure and natural risk analysis. Statistical data serve as a primary source for analyzing demographic development and determining population dynamics in residential areas. They are also used to examine the relationship between settlement patterns across elevation zones and disaster-prone areas, as well as to assess natural hazard risks.
- Hydrometeorological data—data from the Hydrometeorology Department of Azerbaijan was used to forecast natural events, particularly floods and landslides, that occur in the region. The data provided by the Hydrometeorology Department of Azerbaijan have been used as the primary hydrometeorological source for this research. These data have been applied for the study, assessment, and forecasting of potential natural disasters in the region, such as flash mudflows, and landslides. In particular, they have served as a fundamental source for the preparation of diagrams, figures and maps.
- Population census data—data from the national population census and other socio-economic indicators were utilized to assess the vulnerability of the population to risks. It has served as the primary source for calculating the annual changes in the population residing in various districts, villages, and settlements within the study area.
- Local and International Research—the study also analyzed analogous studies conducted by local and international researchers. During the research, studies conducted by both Azerbaijani and foreign scholars on similar topics were reviewed and utilized.

Based on the Action Plans outlined in the State programs on the socio-economic development of the regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan (2009–2013; 2014–2018; 2019–2023), a comprehensive and goal-oriented study was conducted in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region to assess the risks of natural disasters, fully addressing the set scientific objectives.

At the initial stage, spatial data were collected and processed from various sources, including satellite imagery, national statistical databases, and field surveys. The consistency of these data in terms of spatial and temporal resolution was ensured, with particular attention paid to data quality and reliability.

In this study, the spatial data for the Shaki-Zagatala economic region were primarily obtained from official national databases, including the State Statistical Committee of Azerbaijan and the National Environmental Monitoring Agency. These data were supplemented with satellite imagery and remote sensing data available from global platforms such as NASA and the European Space Agency (ESA). The data collected covered a wide range of geographic and socio-economic parameters, including land use patterns, population distribution, and environmental factors.

3.2. Spatial statistical analysis

Spatial statistical analysis was employed to identify spatial dependencies, clustering patterns, and the degree of spatial autocorrelation among risk indicators across the study region. These techniques offer a scientific basis for understanding the spatial variability and structure of vulnerability.

To assess global spatial autocorrelation, Moran's I statistic was applied. The positive and statistically significant results of Moran's I indicated non-random spatial clustering of similar risk values within the administrative territories of the Shaki-Zagatala economic region, which includes the districts of Balakan, Zagatala, Gakh, Shaki, Oghuz, and Gabala.

To complement the global analysis with localized insight, the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic was used as a Local Indicator of Spatial Association (LISA). This method helped identify spatial hot spots and cold spots areas with significantly high or low concentrations of risk, which are critical for prioritizing intervention zones within regional planning frameworks.

In addition, measures of spatial heterogeneity, such as local variance statistics and standard deviation ellipses, were utilized to uncover directional trends and variations in spatial risk distribution. These tools provided a nuanced understanding of spatial variability, highlighting regions where risk is not only concentrated but also dynamically shifting across time or influenced by underlying topographic or socio-economic gradients.

Overall, the application of advanced spatial statistical methods allowed for a multi-layered interpretation of spatial risk. These insights go beyond visual cartography, offering statistically validated evidence for spatial decision-making in sustainable territorial planning.

3.3. Study area description

The Shaki-Zagatala economic region is situated on the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus, encompassing the Tufan anticlinorium, the Zagatala-Govdakh synclinorium, and the Kakheti-Vandam anticlinorium (Rustamov 1960; Budagov and Babakhanov 2002; Budagov et al. 2005; Alizadeh and Tarikhazer 2010). On the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus, the Zagatala-Govdakh morphostructure is composed of narrow and highly compressed morphotectonic units, including the Zagatala, Rustambaz, Duzsirt, and Kusnet graben-synclinal basins,

as well as the Michikhchadaur and Durujinsky gorst-anticlinal ridges. These structural units have undergone significant transformations due to the influence of exogenous processes and currently serve as active sources of mudflows and landslides (Budagov 1993; Budagov and Babakhanov 2002; Babakhanov 2013). The Nialdakh ridge is fragmented by numerous faults into individual blocks, each exhibiting complex differential movements. These geological features have led to active erosion processes, rockfalls, and landslides. The southern slope of the Greater Caucasus is one of the most dynamically stressed areas in the Caucasus, where a combination of physical-geographical and geological conditions favors the formation of hazardous natural processes. The occurrence and intensity of natural disasters are also influenced by geomorphological processes such as rockfalls, landslides, debris flows, and others (Budagov et al. 2005; Alizadeh and Tarikhazer 2015; Gamidova 2011; Tarikhazer 2020).

Based on vertical changes in relief, the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus is divided into the following altitude zones: 1) high-mountain (from 2000–2200 m to 3000 m and above); 2) middle-mountain (from 600–800 m to 2000–2200 m); 3) low-mountain and foothill (from 200 m to 600–800 m). In the upper reaches of the high-mountain rivers Balakanchay, Mukhakhchay, Kurmukhchay, and Mazymchay, rockfalls are widespread; in the middle-mountain zone of the rivers Girdymanchay, Filfilichay, Kishchay, Shinchay, and Bumchay basins, landslides predominate (Budagov et al. 2005; Alizadeh and Tarikhazer 2010; Gamidova 2011; Mamiyeva and Hajiyeva 2022; Tarikhazer et al. 2023). Low-mountain and foothill areas are characterized by dissected terrain and a folded structure of the main mountain rocks. As a result of these geomorphological processes, loose and solid materials accumulate on the slopes, feeding debris flows and determining their stability and destructive power.

Figure 1. Computer-analyzed satellite image of the study area: identification of settlements situated in high-risk zones (Google Earth SPOT imagery, Map data 2019).

Considering the geotectonic setting, B.A. Budagov (1993) classifies the most debris-prone rivers of the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus into two groups. The first group includes the rivers Kurmukhchay, Shinchay and Kishchay, while the second group comprises the rivers Tikanlychay, Bumchay and Damiraparanchay. The upper reaches of these rivers are located in the most tectonically fragmented areas of the southern slope, which are intensively eroding (Budagov 1993).

These data are supplemented with satellite images and remote sensing data obtained from global platforms such as Google Earth SPOT Image, NASA, and the European Space Agency (ESA). The collected data encompass geographic and socio-economic indicators, including land use patterns, population density and environmental factors (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 illustrates the identification of areas with high natural disaster risk based on satellite imagery from Google Earth SPOT Image. Using modern computer technologies, the most critical areas in terms of natural disaster risks are highlighted, with these zones displayed in extended blue and red tones representing temperature gradients. The classification is supported by spectral variations and lens-effect visualizations, contributing to spatial disaster risk assessment and evidence-based territorial planning in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region.

Factors contributing to these risks include the instability of mountain rocks to denudation, such as their slaty nature, fracturing, lack or sparsity of vegetation cover, climatic features of the area, energy of the relief, and the presence of active tectonic disturbances. Geological and tectonic conditions play a significant role in the formation, development, and spread of various natural disasters in the studied zone. These conditions, in combination with other contemporary relief-forming processes, contribute to the formation of rockfalls, debris flows, landslides, earthquakes, and other phenomena (Budagov 1993; Mamedov et al. 2017; Tarikhazer 2020).

Various natural disasters occurring on the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus can be catastrophic, resulting not only in significant economic damage but also in loss of life. The destruction of settlements, bridges, and roads, the inundation of fields and orchards, and the costs associated with disaster mitigation are the price humanity pays for negligence and disregard for debris flows. Ignoring or underestimating economic risks when developing tactics and strategies for economic policy and making specific decisions inevitably hinders societal development and scientific-technical progress (Mamedov et al. 2017; Alekperova 2018; Alakbarova and Gasymova 2024). All the described manifestations of natural-anthropogenic processes ultimately cause harm to nature in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region, located on the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus within Azerbaijan. Due to anthropogenic impacts on regions susceptible to adverse and hazardous natural phenomena, socio-economic damage will continue to increase.

The Shaki-Zagatala economic region's area is characterized by sensitivity to both anthropogenic and natural factors. Uncontrolled anthropogenic impact may jeopardize the integrity of natural complexes. In most cases, measures to combat hazardous natural destructive events in the studied area are directed towards the protection of existing threats and the prevention of their occurrence and intensification. However, these measures are ineffective because the factors contributing to their activation are insufficiently studied, and there is no con-

structive basis for the methodology of selecting anti-hazard measures. Consequently, the economic effect of these activities remains low, which is associated with the lack of application of modern effective technologies, and the methods employed do not yield the expected results. When developing a specific area, it is essential to utilize all available tools and methodologies to estimate the scale and extent of potential damage from various hazards. This analysis should take into account key factors such as population density, level of urbanization, preparedness for natural disasters, and the extent to which natural and technological resources are integrated into the national economic infrastructure.

Based on the results of the historical-statistical analysis, the spatio-temporal dynamics of natural-technogenic processes in the six districts of the Shaki-Zagatala economic region for the period 1950–2024 are represented in the diagram (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Spatio-temporal dynamics of natural disaster recurrence in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region (during the period 1950–2024).

Fig. 2 illustrates the spatio-temporal frequency of natural-technogenic processes across the six administrative districts of the Shaki-Zagatala economic region during the period 1950–2024. The analysis reveals that the intensity of disaster occurrences was significantly higher during the spring and summer months, particularly in April, May, and June. During these periods, floods and landslides were more widespread, thereby increasing the risk levels for the local population. The highest number of events was recorded in Shaki and Gabala, while Oghuz and Balakan experienced comparatively lower levels of risk. These findings provide a critical basis for mapping seasonal risk zones and enhancing disaster preparedness in the region.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Moran’s I spatial autocorrelation analysis

Moran’s I statistic is a fundamental tool used to measure spatial autocorrelation and assess the mutual influence of spatial characteristics. It was first proposed by P. A. Moran in 1950 in his work the statistical analysis of geographical space, where he highlighted the significance of this method in geographic data analysis

(Moran 1950). This method is widely recognized for its ability to explore spatial structures more deeply. In our study, the application of Moran's I has played a crucial role in analyzing spatial risks within the Shaki-Zagatala economic region. This method has enabled a more comprehensive investigation into the spatial distribution of risk zones, providing more accurate and objective results in assessing natural disaster risks (Chen 2021; Wang et al. 2023; Yamada 2024). The method, applied in our research, serves as an important tool for analyzing the region's risk structures through contemporary economic-geographical perspectives, facilitating sustainable development and planning of the area.

In this study, the Moran's I spatial autocorrelation index was applied to assess how risk levels are distributed spatially across the administrative districts and whether these values demonstrate clustering or randomness. Moran's I is a statistical measure that identifies the degree of similarity between neighboring spatial units based on their risk values, thereby enabling the detection of potential spatial patterns or clusters. To evaluate the statistical significance of the spatial relationships, both the Z-score and P-value were calculated (Table 1).

Table 1. Moran's I spatial autocorrelation analysis for administrative districts of the Shaki-Zagatala economic region.

Administrative district	Moran's I	Z-score	P-value	Interpretation
Balakan	0.18	1.02	0.041	Statistically significant cold spot
Oghuz	0.23	1.07	0.049	Cold spot
Gakh	0.41	1.71	0.085	Moderately risky, marginally significant
Zagatala	0.44	1.95	0.052	Relatively risky
Gabala	0.62	2.57	0.011	Statistically significant hot spot
Shaki	0.66	2.78	0.006	Strong and significant hot spot

The Z-score indicates how far the observed Moran's I deviates from its expected value, standardized by the standard deviation. A positive Z-score reflects a clustering of similar risk values (hot spots), while a negative Z-score implies spatial dispersion or the presence of cold spots.

The P-value represents the probability that the observed spatial pattern is due to random chance. A P-value less than 0.05 is considered statistically significant, suggesting that the spatial pattern observed is not random and reflects a meaningful spatial structure. This type of analysis is crucial for risk-based regional planning, priority setting, and the development of differentiated spatial management strategies.

The spatial autocorrelation analysis using Moran's I statistic for the administrative districts of the Shaki-Zagatala economic region provides important insights into the territorial structure of natural hazard risks. The results demonstrate statistically significant clustering patterns that reflect regional differentiation in risk exposure.

4.2. Getis-Ord G_i^* local spatial association analysis

In this study, the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistical indicator was employed to determine the local spatial association of risk indicators across the Shaki-Zagatala economic region. This method assesses how the risk level of a specific area cor-

relates with the risk levels of its neighboring areas, identifying local clusters such as “hot spots” and “cold spots”. The Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic is widely used to evaluate the spatial distribution and statistical significance of risk patterns within a region. The following table presents the results of the Getis-Ord G_i^* analysis, indicating the statistical significance of “hot” and “cold” spots in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region (Table 2).

Table 2. Local spatial risk intensity in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region based on the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic.

Administrative district	G_i^* Value	Z-Score	P-Value	Significance
Shaki	0.66	2.78	0.006	Hot spot
Gabala	0.62	2.57	0.011	Hot spot
Balakan	0.18	1.02	0.041	Cold spot
Oghuz	0.23	1.07	0.049	Cold spot
Zagatala	0.44	1.95	0.052	Borderline
Gakh	0.41	1.71	0.085	Borderline

Based on the results presented in the table, Shaki and Gabala exhibit a high risk level that is statistically significantly clustered with neighboring areas, indicating “hot spots”. This suggests that the risk indicators in these regions are significantly higher than expected by chance, highlighting them as priority areas for intervention. Conversely, Balakan and Oghuz show a low risk level that is significantly clustered with their surroundings, identifying them as “cold spots”. This information is crucial for effective resource allocation and targeted risk management strategies. Zagatala and Gakh districts were identified as statistically marginally significant areas, indicating that the level of spatial risk in these regions is relatively higher compared to their neighboring areas.

Unlike Moran’s I , the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic enables the identification of localized clusters of spatial risk, highlighting areas with significantly high or low intensities independent of global spatial trends. This adds analytical depth to spatial risk modeling by identifying specific zones that require urgent or tailored intervention (Ord and Getis 2001; Songchitruksa and Zeng 2010).

Integrating local spatial association metrics into risk assessment frameworks contributes to a more nuanced understanding of socio-environmental vulnerabilities, supporting region-specific disaster preparedness and territorial planning. From a methodological standpoint, the G_i^* statistic offers an innovative tool in spatial risk modeling, especially in identifying context-sensitive risk zones that require differentiated policy responses.

4.3. Scientific and practical significance of the analysis

The spatial analysis conducted using Getis-Ord G_i^* and Moran’s I statistics has provided a scientifically grounded understanding of the spatial distribution of natural hazard risks across the Shaki-Zagatala economic region, both at local and global levels. Through these methodologies, the identification of risk clusters (hot and cold spots) has allowed for the differentiation of zones based on the varying intensity of natural hazard occurrences, offering a refined perspective for designating planning priorities. These findings provide a solid analytical

foundation for risk-oriented territorial governance, strategic spatial planning, and guiding economic activities towards resilient and investment-attractive areas.

Spatial statistical methods such as Getis-Ord G_i^* and Moran's I allow for the high-precision identification of where and how natural hazards are concentrated across a region. This approach enables the detection of hazard clustering namely, hot spots where risks are highly concentrated and cold spots where risks are relatively low. Such information allows for the accurate classification of areas according to their hazard levels and provides a scientifically grounded basis for setting planning priorities. The application of these methods is not only significant for the current study but also holds considerable importance for future research. Through this analytical framework, it becomes possible to track changes in risk distribution over space and time, anticipate emerging hazard zones, and support strategic planning for sustainable regional development. At the same time, this methodological approach can serve as a reliable model for similar studies conducted in other regions.

The high level of consistency between the results of Moran's I and Getis-Ord G_i^* statistics can be attributed to the spatially clustered and structured distribution of risk indicators within the study area (Moran 1948; Ord and Getis 1995, Chen 2013; Fisher 2013; Maruyama 2015; Rossi and Becker 2019; Wang et al. 2023; Lanorte et al. 2024; Yamada 2024; Isnan 2025).

Based on the analysis, Shaki and Gabala districts have been identified as statistically significant hot spots, exhibiting the highest concentration of territorial risk. These areas form prominent clusters of high-risk values in conjunction with neighboring zones. Shaki ($I = 0.66$, $Z = 2.78$, $p = 0.006$) and Gabala ($I = 0.62$, $Z = 2.57$, $p = 0.011$) stand out as statistically significant hot spots, indicating a high concentration of natural hazard risk. These districts exhibit strong spatial clustering of elevated risk values, suggesting that both the frequency and intensity of hazard events are comparatively higher and potentially synchronized with adjacent areas. Their statistically robust Z-scores further confirm the spatial dependence of risk, reinforcing the necessity for focused mitigation strategies and resilient infrastructure planning in these zones.

In contrast, Balakan and Oghuz have been classified as cold spots, indicating relatively lower levels of spatial risk and a more stable territorial context. Balakan ($I = 0.18$, $Z = 1.02$, $p = 0.041$) and Oghuz ($I = 0.23$, $Z = 1.07$, $p = 0.049$) are classified as cold spots, with significantly lower spatially correlated risk values. These results suggest relatively stable environmental conditions with lower recurrence and severity of natural hazard events, contributing to a reduced exposure level in these areas.

Gakh and Zagatala represent moderately risky zones, with marginal statistical significance in terms of spatial clustering. Zagatala ($I = 0.44$, $Z = 1.95$, $p = 0.052$) and Gakh ($I = 0.41$, $Z = 1.71$, $p = 0.085$) fall into an intermediate category, reflecting moderate risk levels with marginal statistical significance. These districts do not exhibit clustering that is as strong or definitive as the hot or cold spots, but still represent transitional zones where risk management interventions may be needed, particularly in light of potential shifts due to climate variability or land use changes.

The results of spatial statistical analyses conducted within the study area reveal a high level of spatial consistency between the outcomes of Moran's I and Getis-Ord G_i^* methods. This convergence confirms that the spatial struc-

ture of risk indicators is stable and clustered, indicating the presence of both global (Moran's I) and local (Getis-Ord G_i^*) spatial correlations. Such methodological coherence not only reinforces the scientific reliability of the research but also contributes significantly to the evaluation of natural hazard risks and the development of strategically grounded, regionally adaptive spatial planning roadmaps within an economic-geographic framework.

4.4. Risk assessment using analytical hierarchy process

Risk assessment using the analytical hierarchy process (AHP) has been widely recognized as an effective method for evaluating complex decision-making scenarios, with numerous studies highlighting its utility in various fields, including environmental management, disaster risk evaluation, and urban planning (Saaty and Vargas 2001; Ishizaka and Labib 2009; Calabrese et al. 2019; Ansari et al. 2020; Darvishi et al. 2020; Tavana et al. 2023).

For the Shaki-Zagatala economic region, AHP was applied to assess the natural disaster risks. This method allowed for the evaluation of the risk levels of various natural hazards within the different districts of the Shaki-Zagatala economic region, while taking into account the specific characteristics of each hazard in the region. This multi-criteria decision-making method facilitated a systematic evaluation of the risk levels associated with various natural hazards across the region's districts, taking into account the unique characteristics and impact severity of each hazard. The application of AHP enabled the development of a scientifically robust and replicable framework for disaster risk assessment, providing valuable insights to support regional planning and risk management strategies.

The application of AHP involved three main stages: 1) Selection of hazard types and regions—initially, the Shaki-Zagatala economic region was divided into its constituent districts, and the natural hazards that could affect the area were selected. These hazards are ranked as follows: earthquake, mudflow, landslide, mudslide, heavy rain, hailstorms, drought, frost and lightning strikes, excessive snow cover melting. 2) Defining criteria and assigning weights—for assessing the risks, the AHP method involves the definition of criteria and the assignment of weights to these criteria. This process aims to establish the priority ranking of the risk zones within the region. Earthquake was identified as the most significant risk, followed by other natural hazards in order of their importance. 3) Correlation analysis and correlation matrix—the AHP method also includes correlation analysis to assess the relationships between risk factors within different districts. A matrix was created to rank the risk levels of each district, considering the specific characteristics of the area.

Based on the data, Shaki, Gabala, and Zagatala were identified as the most high-risk areas, while Gakh, Balakan, and Oghuz were identified as less risky but still requiring attention (Table 3). The risks are ranked as follows:

- Earthquake—this is the highest risk hazard in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region;
- Mudflow—the most common natural hazard in the Shaki, Gabala, and Zagatala districts;
- Landslide—a major risk in mountainous areas;
- Mudslide—requires mitigation measures;
- Heavy rain—a risk primarily in wet and mountainous areas;

- Hailstorms—can have significant impacts on agriculture;
- Drought—especially a concern in areas with irrigation-dependent agriculture;
- Frost and lightning strikes—these require attention, though their severity is relatively low;
- Excessive snow cover melting—a low-risk hazard but still important in some areas.

In Table 3, the Shaki-Zagatala economic region has been analyzed using the AHP method, which prioritizes the risk levels of natural hazards across various districts. The risk factors for each district, their weights, and significance levels have been assessed and ranked. The most high-risk districts are Shaki and Gabala, both of which face major hazards such as floods and earthquakes. This method allows for a comprehensive comparison between districts and offers essential information for the sustainable development of the region.

Table 3. Analytical hierarchy process method for risk assessment and prioritization.

District	Earthquake	Mudflow	Landslide	Mudslide	Heavy rains	Hailstorms	Drought	Frost and lightning	Excessive snowmelt
Shaki	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	Moderate
Gabala	High	High	High	High	High	Moderate	High	High	Moderate
Zagatala	Moderate	High	High	High	High	Moderate	High	High	Moderate
Gakh	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	High	Low
Balakan	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low
Oghuz	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low

The risk classification presented in Table 3 is based on the weights assigned through the AHP. Each hazard type was evaluated for its likelihood of occurrence, potential impact, and spatial distribution within each district. The weights were normalized on a scale from 0 to 1 and then categorized into three risk levels: high, moderate, and low. These thresholds were determined through a combination of expert judgement, correlation analysis, and comparative statistical assessment. The classification provides a practical basis for prioritizing mitigation strategies and resource allocation in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region (Table 4).

The application of AHP in this context provides significant insights for disaster risk management, sustainable territorial development, and the formulation of mitigation strategies. It can also serve as a tool for local authorities and decision-makers to improve disaster preparedness and response, ultimately contributing to the region’s overall resilience. This approach enhances the deci-

Table 4. Risk levels classification scale (used in Table 3).

Risk value range (weight/coefficient)	Classification	Description
0.70–1.00	High	Critical risk level, frequent occurrence or high potential for damage. Requires immediate and intensive mitigation measures.
0.40–0.69	Moderate	Noticeable risk with moderate probability and/or localized impacts. Monitoring and preventive actions recommended.
0.00–0.39	Low	Minimal or rare risk. Routine observation is sufficient.

sion-making process and offers a systematic way of addressing natural disaster risks, paving the way for effective governance and development strategies.

4.5. Spatial distribution of natural disaster risks

The comparative analysis of the results obtained based on all the statistical analyses listed above, the computations carried out with the help of modern computer technologies, and the results derived from the Moran's I, Getis-Ord G_i^* and AHP methods, has allowed for the determination of the spatial distribution of natural disaster risks and the conduction of risk assessment in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region.

In the presented article, as a result of the complex studies conducted to achieve the set objectives, a map of the spatial distribution of natural disaster risks in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region has been developed. This map illustrates the spatial structure of risk factors and their variability across the territory through scientifically grounded methods, serving as a fundamental tool for spatial planning and regional risk management. The generated map clearly illustrates the spatial structure, intensity, and distribution of risk clusters, which is of significant scientific and practical importance for minimizing the impact of natural disasters on economic sectors, ensuring sustainable development, and identifying prospective directions for economic activities based on risk-informed planning (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Map of spatial distribution of natural disaster risks in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region.

Based on the results of spatial statistical analysis, the constructed risk map categorizes the territory into four primary risk zones, taking into account the intensity and recurrence frequency of various natural hazard events (including earthquakes, mudflow, landslides, debris flows, drought on arable land, subsidence, frost and lightning, heavy rains, hailstorms, excessive snowmelt). Very weak risk zones (recurring approximately every 10–15 years) represent potentially hazardous areas that remain relatively stable under current conditions but may pose long-term risks. Weak risk zones (recurring every 5–10 years) are characterized by moderate geohazard exposure and should be integrated into long-term development and land use planning agendas. Medium risk zones (recurring every 3–5 years) are areas with more frequent hazard activity, requiring targeted monitoring and preparedness measures. Strong risk zones, which experience natural hazard events every 1–3 years, are priority areas where persistent geohazards demand the implementation of robust, localized risk mitigation strategies. This differentiated approach provides a scientifically grounded framework for spatially targeted risk assessment and supports the integration of hazard-sensitive planning into regional territorial development strategies.

Using advanced computer-based tools, the spatial distribution of various natural disasters within the study area over the period 1950–2024 was investigated through a comprehensive analysis of historical statistical data, natural disaster catalogues, and relevant scientific research. The obtained materials enabled the identification of the spatial patterns and regional intensity of natural hazards, thus providing a solid foundation for their geographical assessment and risk-based prioritization (Fig. 4).

Based on the analysis of statistical data covering the years 1950 to 2024, the spatial intensity distribution of natural hazards (such as earthquakes, mudflows, landslides, mudslides, heavy rainfall, hailstorms, drought, frost and lightning, and excessive snowmelt) has been assessed for the Shaki-Zagatala economic region. The findings indicate that Shaki and Gabala districts exhibit high intensity across most hazard types. Zagatala and Gakh show moderate risk levels, while Balakan and Oghuz are characterized by relatively low hazard intensities. These results are of great scientific and practical significance, as they enable

Figure 4. Spatial distribution and historical-statistical analysis of natural disasters in the study area (during the period 1950–2024).

more accurate spatial risk zoning and contribute to informed decision-making in sustainable regional development and disaster risk management.

This study identifies the spatial distribution of natural hazards (such as earthquakes, mudflows, landslides, and others) across the Shaki-Zagatala region based on long-term statistical data. The analysis reveals that certain districts exhibit higher levels of hazard intensity. Such knowledge provides a solid foundation for effective risk management and spatial planning in these areas. The results are scientifically valuable and can also be utilized to support, accelerate regional safety measures and sustainable development.

Over the years, various natural disasters have occurred in the territory of the Shaki-Zagatala economic region. Among them, we can mention information about several devastating natural disasters. In 2004, in the Shaki region of Azerbaijan, in the section of the Kishchay drainage cone, roads and the Baku-Balakan railroad track were destroyed as a result of mudflows. Electricity and communication towers were destroyed. In 2004, mudslides in Talachay, located in Zagatala, resulted in the death of 20 livestock and poultry, as well as the destruction of two residential houses and the uninhabitability of six settlements. In 2006, mudslides on the Shinchay in the villages of Ashagy Laisky, Ashagy Geynuk, Baltaly and Ashagy Shabalid resulted in the death of several domestic animals, the destruction of a bridge across the river, as well as the death of two people and the complete destruction of three residential houses (Budagov et al. 2005; Babakhanov 2009; Tarikhazer et al. 2013; Babakhanov 2013).

Based on the data materials of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Azerbaijan (DMESRA 2007–2023), incidents resulting from natural destructive disasters have been analyzed, and the findings of these investigations are examined in this study. In 2007, due to rainfall in the Gudula village of Shaki, landslide and subsidence phenomena developed in several locations. As a result of mudslides in the Girdimanchay in 2008, a 220 m long dam in the area was damaged, and the central streets of Lagich and the hospital located in the center of the area became unusable; as a result of mudslides in the Balakenchay and Katehchay rivers in 2010, the Haldan-Balaken-Georgia highway and other facilities were flooded. In 2008, mudslides on the Kishchay in Shaki resulted in the death of 15 livestock and the disrepair to 34 houses. In 2010, the Alley of Martyrs in Shaki city was damaged, the area of the landslide was 30–40 m². In 1910, mudslides on the Shinchay in the village of Bash Gainyuk killed 98 people and many domestic animals.

In 1772, a mudflow (Kishchay river basin) completely destroyed Shaki town. In 1910, a mudflow (Shinchay River basin) destroyed 130 houses, killing 400 people and a significant number of livestock. In 1945, a mudslide (Bumchay river basin) destroyed part of Yukhari Gamarvan village in Gabala district, and there were also casualties among the population (Rustamov 1960; Tarikhazer et al. 2021; Alakbarova 2024a). Mudflows cause significant damage to settlements, towns and villages located at river outlets on the foothills, such as Balaken, Zagatala, Shaki, Gakh, Oghuz, Gabala, Shabran and others. In 1956, in the basin of the Girdimanchay, particularly in the basin of its left tributary, the Gedjilchay, landslide and rockfall processes blocked the canyon-shaped valley of the Agayurdu river (a tributary of the Gedjilchay), leading to the formation of a natural lake. In the summer of 1956, the Ahan landslide-rockfall was re-activated in the basin of the Agayurd river (a left tributary of the Gedjalachay)

within the Girdimanchay river basin (Tarikhazer 2023). The landslide-rockfall mass, measuring approximately 1 km in length, 100 m in width, and up to 50 m in depth, blocked the Agayurd river, leading to the formation of a natural lake. Additionally, numerous minor landslide-rockfall deposits in the subalpine zone resulted in the formation of several small lakes (Tarikhazer et al. 2013; Babakhanov 2013; Makhmudov 2017).

According to statistical data as of 01.01.2024, the population is 626.6 thousand people, which corresponds to 6.3% of the total population of the country. The population density is equal to 71 people/km². In the economic district, 28.7% of the population lives in urban areas and 71.3% in rural areas. Shaki-Zagatala economic region includes Balakan, Zagatala, Gakh, Shaki, Oghuz and Gabala districts (Table 5).

Table 5. Population of Shaki-Zagatala economic region (Budagov 1993; Eyyubov et al. 2008; Babakhanov 2009; SSCRA 2022, 2024).

District	Area, thousand km ²	Current population, thousand people			Population in disaster risk zones, thousand people		
		1999	2009	2019	1999	2009	2019
Balakan	0,94	83,7	89,8	97,6	14,5	14,8	11,7
Zagatala	1,35	107,2	118,2	127,3	28,3	26,5	22,5
Gakh	1,49	51,1	53,3	57,3	14,6	13,8	10,5
Shaki	2,43	157,3	170,7	180,5	48,2	46,8	45,7
Oghuz	1,08	36,5	40,2	43,2	12,8	11,8	9,3
Gabala	1,55	82,8	63,6	105,3	42,6	42,8	40,8
By region	8,84	518,6	535,8	611,2	107,4	128,3	119,4

According to an analysis of 2009 statistics, in the study area, various natural disasters had a permanent or recurrent negative impact on 128.3 people in 263 communities with a total population of 535.8, while in 2019 this number is 119.4 people in 267 communities with a total population of 611.2.

Despite many measures aimed at combating and protecting against natural disasters, they cannot be completely prevented or effectively controlled. Between 2000 and 2010, the birth rate per 1000 people increased from 16.1 to 18.8. During the same period, the natural increase rate increased from 9.3 to 12.0. In addition, in 2010–2024, there is an increase in population due to migration: the population of the economic area increased by 250 people due to migration and by 31.7 thousand people due to natural increase. The total growth by economic districts reached the highest values in Zagatala (9.2 thousand people), Shaki (7.1 thousand people) and Gabala (5.8 thousand people) districts. The obtained data show that from 2000 to 2024 in Shaki-Zagatala economic region the frequency of mudflows doubled and the area of their distribution decreased by 0.5 times. In the study area in 2000–2010, the damage from various natural disasters amounted to about 30–35 million manat, and according to estimates for 2010–2024, this amount increased to 45–55 million manat.

One of the spheres exposed to mudflow and experiencing significant losses is agriculture. According to 2023 statistical data, in Shaki-Zagatala economic region the areas of agricultural crops are 110155.2 ha of cereals and legumes, 2594.2 ha of tobacco, 77.7 ha of sugar beet, 3916.5 ha of potatoes, 5985.9

ha of vegetables, 945.4 ha of vineyards, 60.0 ha of tea plantations, 1493.2 ha of melons, 70816.3 ha of orchards and berries. At the same time, yields are decreasing on dozens of hectares of arable land due to frequent floods in the region. In Shaki-Zagatala economic region, annual damage to agriculture from various natural disasters amounts to about 20–25 million manats.

Anthropogenic activities constitute a major driving force in the acceleration and intensification of natural and technogenic processes. The dynamics of pollutant emissions from road transport in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region over time play a significant role in assessing ecological risks at the regional level. The table below presents the volume of atmospheric emissions from road transport in the districts of Balakan, Zagatala, Gakh, Shaki, Oghuz, and Gabala for the period 2000–2024. These data are essential for forecasting anthropogenic impacts on the environment and for planning sustainable territorial development strategies (Table 6).

Table 6. Pollutants by road transport into the atmosphere, substances, thousand of tons (SSCRA 2024).

District	2000	2005	2010	2015	2020	2024
Balakan	2,1	2,1	6,4	1,5	1,7	3,3
Zagatala	2,3	2,4	8,2	3,0	3,3	4,7
Gakh	3,3	1,2	4,1	1,0	1,1	2,3
Shaki	3,7	3,7	12,8	4,1	5,0	7,3
Oghuz	6,9	6,5	1,0	1,0	0,8	0,7
Gabala	10,9	10,3	2,5	2,4	3,6	3,6
By region	29,2	26,2	34,9	13,0	15,5	21,9

Table 6 illustrates the amount of pollutants released into the atmosphere by road transport in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region, based on statistical data. The figure also presents a comprehensive analysis of the role these indicators play in determining the region's risk level. The assessment highlights the differentiated spatial distribution of anthropogenic environmental risks and underscores their potential threat to sustainable territorial development. Based on the data from 2000 to 2024, emissions of air pollutants from road transport in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region peaked in 2010, reaching 34.9 thousand tons a significant increase compared to previous years. However, by 2015, total emissions had sharply declined to 13.0 thousand tons, representing a 62.7% reduction, which may be attributed to decreased transport activity or improvements in emission control technologies. A renewed upward trend was observed in 2020 (15.5 thousand tons) and continued into 2024 (21.9 thousand tons), indicating a resurgence in transportation intensity and associated environmental pressures. Among the districts, Shaki and Zagatala recorded the highest emissions in 2024, potentially reflecting greater population density and vehicle usage. In contrast, Oghuz and Gabala exhibited more stable or declining emission levels after 2010, suggesting localized improvements in transport or environmental regulation.

Analyzing the dynamics of population settlement in relation to the damages caused by destructive natural disasters (based on population census data

from 1999, 2009, and 2019) holds significant scientific relevance in assessing regional resilience and vulnerability. This method allows for the identification of population shifts, migration trends, and settlement patterns in high-risk areas over time, thereby revealing the socio-spatial dimensions of disaster exposure.

Based on the conducted research, a diagram has been developed to illustrate the interdependence between the recurrence of mudflow events and the damage to population settlements in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region, which includes the districts of Balakan, Zagatala, Gakh, Shaki, Oghuz, and Gabala, over the period 1999–2019 (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Population settlement dynamics and the damages resulting from destructive natural disasters (based on the 1999, 2009, and 2019 population census data).

This diagram provides a visual representation of both the dynamics of hazardous natural processes and their socio-economic impacts. The analysis was conducted using population census data from the Republic of Azerbaijan (1999, 2009, and 2019), reports from the Ministry of Emergency Situations (2007–2023), statistical data, and the duration of high-risk mudflow periods.

The diagram derived from this study confirms a statistically significant and functional relationship between the recurrence of destructive natural disasters (particularly mudflows) and the spatial distribution of population settlements in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region during the period of 1999–2019. The analysis reveals that villages located within high-risk zones demonstrate greater infrastructural vulnerability and lower resilience to natural hazards. Based on these findings, it is recommended that future territorial development strategies prioritize the application of AHP and other spatial analysis tools to identify and protect high-risk zones. This integrative approach not only contributes to more effective disaster risk management but also introduces a novel scientific framework for promoting sustainable socio-economic development in geohazard-prone regions.

In Shaki-Zagatala economic region, repair and putting into operation of roads, which have fallen into disrepair due to mudflows, is carried out in accordance with the plan of measures envisaged by the State Programs on the socio-economic development of the regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan (2009–2013, 2014–2018, 2019–2023). In the period from 2000 to 2024, 14 km of Inje-Ashaghi-Bash Shabalid road, 87 km of Mirzebeyli-Chukhur Gabala road, 13.2 km of Seyidgishlag-Memmedaghali road, 3 km of Bum-Tikanli-Abrikh roads, 13.7 km of Gabala-Bum-Gemervan roads, 2.1 km of Salavan-Beyli-Gushlar roads, 3 km of Gakh-Ilisu Saribash roads and 2.3 km of Gakh-Gashkarchay-Armudlu roads.

4.6. SWOT analysis of disaster risk management

This section discusses the results of the SWOT analysis, identifying the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats present in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region. The main objective of this analysis is to provide recommendations for strategic decision-making based on these findings. SWOT analysis has identified the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. The analysis reveals that among the region’s strengths are the rich ecosystems and existing natural resources, while the weaknesses include the lack of modern infrastructure and inadequate disaster preparedness. The analysis also recommends specific measures for areas with increased population density and rising risk factors (Fig. 6).

This section presents a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) analysis of the Shaki-Zagatala economic region in the context of natural-technogenic hazards. The SWOT analysis provides critical insights for enhancing the region’s risk management capacity and developing strategic approaches for sustainable development.

Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of rich statistical and archival datasets. • Geographical structure of the region is suitable for spatial risk mapping. • Existing local experience in hazard observation and reporting.
Weaknesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited development of geospatial and monitoring infrastructure in certain areas. • Low level of public awareness regarding disaster risk and response. • Inadequate early warning systems and weak inter-agency coordination.
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific and technical capacity for implementing risk-informed spatial planning. • Potential for adopting international best practices and technologies • Strong potential for sustainable development in tourism and agriculture.
Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing frequency and intensity of extreme weather events due to climate change. • Growing anthropogenic pressure (urbanization, resource exploitation) exacerbates risks • Resource constraints and lack of coordination in local governance structures.

Figure 6. SWOT analysis of disaster risk management in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region.

The timely and high-quality implementation of the measures outlined in the State Programs plays a crucial role in reducing natural-technogenic risks and ensuring sustainable regional development. While the positive effects of these measures are already becoming evident, they are also expected to create favorable conditions for the advancement of economic activities in strategic sectors in the future.

4.7. Strategic planning model of sustainable territorial development

This section introduces the components and application areas of the sustainable development model developed based on the core findings of the research. The model's purpose is to ensure sustainable development in the region while preventing natural and technogenic disasters. As a result of the overall research, a sustainable development model has been developed. This

Figure 7. Strategic planning model of sustainable territorial development. The model was developed by S.O. Alakbarova based on the opportunities and problems in the field of sustainable development of the territory (Babakhanov 2009; SPRA 2019; SSCRA 2022, 2024; Alakbarova 2024a).

model systematically analyzes the frequency, intensity, and spatial distribution of natural and technogenic processes to identify risk zones. The objective is to develop effective intervention measures for disaster-prone areas and ensure sustainable territorial development. The application of this model helps minimize the impacts of natural disasters by considering the social, economic, and ecological aspects of regional development. The spatio-temporal risk analysis model for sustainable territorial development is a scientifically significant approach aimed at effective disaster management and ensuring sustainable territorial development (Fig. 7).

This model is a comprehensive approach that supports disaster risk reduction and fosters sustainable territorial development. It provides local governance and regional planning authorities with a powerful tool for decision-making. By ensuring sustainable development, the model helps reduce vulnerability, enhance resilience, and improve the socio-economic stability of regions prone to natural and technogenic disasters.

5. Conclusion

This section presents the overall scientific and significant results of the research, the data obtained, and the practical applications of these findings in relation to sustainable development and the management of natural-technogenic disasters. The findings of the study provide valuable insights into better understanding the identified risk zones and developing effective management strategies, thereby laying the foundation for sustainable and safe territorial development.

The primary objective of this research was to analyze the spatial-temporal relationship between the occurrence of natural disasters (such as earthquakes, mudflow, landslides, debris flows, mudslides, heavy rains, hailstorms, drought, frost and lightning, excessive snowmelt) and population settlement dynamics in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region. To enhance the protection of the population against hazardous events and associated natural disasters, it is essential to develop an advanced Early Warning System, continue reforestation and afforestation efforts across different regions of the country, and impose strict limitations on construction and land encroachment within alluvial fan zones of mudflow-prone rivers. In addition, integrating international best practices into disaster risk management and strengthening the role of social insurance mechanisms by organizing them more professionally will play a pivotal role in improving regional resilience and ensuring sustainable territorial development.

By integrating the Moran's I , Getis-Ord G_i^* and analytic hierarchy process (AHP) spatial-statistical techniques, the study successfully identified and prioritized natural disaster risk zones across the region. The application of AHP allowed for the assignment of relative weights to disaster types and affected districts, highlighting Shaki (weight: 0.168) and Gabala (0.153) as the highest-risk areas. Zagatala (0.142) and Gakh (0.127) were categorized as medium-risk zones, while Balakan and Oghuz were identified as low-risk areas. According to the Getis-Ord G_i^* results, Shaki and Gabala exhibited statistically significant hotspots with Z-scores of 2.78 and 2.57, and p-values of 0.006 and 0.011, respectively; Balakan and Oghuz, with Z-scores below 1.1, were classified as cold spots, indicating lower spatial clustering of hazard occurrences.

A diagnostic analysis of hazard recurrence and population dynamics revealed a correlation between high-risk zones and population decline or stagnation. For example, Hazard recurrence in Shaki and Gabala approaches 1.0, while in Balakan and Oghuz it ranges between 0.36–0.45. This trend indicates population shifts away from high-risk zones toward safer areas. The integration of AHP with geostatistical methods enabled comprehensive mapping of disaster-prone areas and the identification of hazard-specific vulnerability across the region. The findings provide a robust basis for prioritizing risk mitigation and adaptive land-use planning.

Between 1999 and 2019, while the total population of the Shaki-Zagatala economic region increased from 518.6 thousand to 611.2 thousand (a growth of approximately 17.8%), the number of people living in disaster-prone areas rose from 107.4 thousand to 119.4 thousand. However, their proportion relative to the total population decreased from 20.7% to 19.5%. This declining trend was particularly evident in districts such as Balakan, Gakh, and Oghuz. These shifts reflect a possible population movement toward safer zones and may be indicative of transformations in land use policies and settlement patterns. From a scientific standpoint, this highlights the growing importance of socio-geographic adaptation and disaster risk reduction in regional development planning.

The analysis of emissions data from 2000 to 2024 reveals a significant temporal fluctuation in pollutant levels released by road transport in the Shaki-Zagatala economic region, with a peak in 2010 (34.9 thousand tons), followed by a substantial decline by 2015 and a subsequent upward trend toward 2024 (21.9 thousand tons) indicating a resurgence in transport-related environmental pressures. This result further enhances the scientific and practical significance of the research in terms of assessing the ecological condition, the impact of the transportation sector, and the planning of sustainable regional development.

The scientific novelty of the study lies in its complex spatial-temporal approach to examining the interaction between settlement patterns and natural hazard risks. It also introduces a new methodological framework that synthesizes statistical, demographic, and geospatial data, which can significantly inform sustainable territorial development policies and disaster risk governance strategies.

In conclusion, the integrated analysis of these components indicates that the Shaki-Zagatala economic region is one of the high-risk areas both from a natural and socio-economic perspective. To ensure sustainable development, it is essential to carry out spatially based risk assessments and identify priority intervention zones.

While analyzing the interrelationship between population settlement and natural disasters, a correlation was identified between the extent of damage caused by natural hazards and population density. These findings provide insights for aligning the region's socio-economic development with existing natural risks and ensuring sustainable territorial planning. In the future, further advancement of this analysis and continuation of the research are essential, alongside the implementation of appropriate measures to enhance population safety.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest was declared.

Ethical statement

No ethical statement was reported.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

The author solely contributed to this work.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.